

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in Netherlands

Country report

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Executive Summary

This document outlines insights from the I-CLAIM public perceptions survey on irregular migration, which on what people in the Netherlands know about irregular migration, how they perceive it, and their attitudes toward irregular migrants, particularly in relation to work and employment. The survey was carried out in the Netherlands in February 2025 with a nationally representative sample of 1,052 adults.

Findings from the survey point to gaps in knowledge, especially regarding the estimation of the share of irregular migrants in the Netherlands. While estimates of irregular migration suggest that irregular migrants account for between 1.4% and 3.6% foreign-born population, respondents greatly overestimated this figure. Overestimation was particularly pronounced among older and right-leaning respondents.

Gaps in knowledge also exist regarding probable pathways into irregularity. When asked about possible scenarios leading to irregularity, respondents mainly linked them to unauthorized border crossings and pending asylum claims, patterns that mirror dominant political and media narratives. More routine or administrative pathways to irregularity, such as overstaying a visa or losing lawful residence after changes in employment, processes that research shows are central to the production of irregular status, were less often recognised as leading to irregularity.

Attitudes toward, and perceptions of, irregular migrants as workers were mixed. Respondents identified food delivery, construction, hospitality, cleaning, and care as the main sectors of irregular employment. They added sex work in the open questions as a sector where it was expected to have many irregular migrants working. They indicated some level of unease toward irregular migrants, especially if encountered within their home or work settings.

Hiring experiments revealed pragmatic choices: candidates with longer Dutch residence, good recommendations, and family ties in the country were favoured, even if irregular. However, racialised hierarchies shaped these choices, with candidates from Morocco less favoured than those from Brazil.

Perceptions of integration were tied to socio-cultural indicators, such as Dutch fluency and the presence of family and friends in the Netherlands.

Overall, the survey suggests that views on irregular migration in the Netherlands are fragmented and often distorted. Attitudes combine suspicion and pragmatic considerations, and demonstrated the importance of social markers of belonging. These findings highlight the need to address misperceptions and the wider narrative environment that shapes public debates on irregularity.

1. Introduction

Irregular migration can be defined as a situation where foreign nationals residing in a given country do not hold legal residence due to different circumstance. Public knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants is limited. In this report, which presents main findings from an online survey conducted in February 2025 on public perceptions of irregular migration conducted among the public of the Netherlands, we aim to address this gap in evidence. The survey forms part of the Horizon Europe-funded project “Improving the living and labour conditions of irregularised migrant households in Europe” (I-CLAIM) and focuses on public perceptions of irregular migration and irregular migrants in general, but particularly in relation to work and employment. This report uses harmonised analyses and the blueprint provided by the UK report (Lessard-Phillips and Sigona, 2025), to showcase the results of the survey.

This builds on earlier work (Hajer 2024) that examined the narrative construction of migrant irregularity in the Netherlands across three primary domains: media, politics, and civil society. In that work, we examined how different stakeholders frame and influence public discourse on irregular migration, with particular attention to the intersection of employment, gender, race, and family-related representations.

Overall, our work highlighted the construction, and contestation, of public narratives across media, politics, and civil society. It highlighted a disconnect between dominant narratives—often fixated on border crossings—and the complex realities of a phenomenon shaped by Dutch and European immigration and labour policies in addition to governance.

The I-CLAIM survey is informed by these research findings as well as the concept of ‘irregularity assemblage’ (Gonzales et al. 2019; Sigona et al. 2021, Sigona & van Liempt 2025). This approach emphasises irregularity as a dynamic position rather than a state-imposed fixed status that is co-constructed at the intersection of different regulatory frameworks (Gonzales et al., 2019). The approach includes migrants without legal residence, but also migrants increasingly at risk of irregularisation due to structural features of the immigration system.

In light of this, the survey explores who the Dutch public considers “irregular,” what meaning they attach to this label, and how these perceptions influence their attitudes. It does so through the use of ‘traditional’ as well as ‘experimental’ survey questions and aims to contribute to developing evidence based on irregular migration and irregular migrants.

This report starts by providing information about the survey and the sample of respondents before exploring two main themes based on the following questions:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants?
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work?

2. About the Survey

2.1. Development and methodology

The I-CLAIM survey aimed to capture perceptions of, and attitudes toward, irregularity among the Dutch public. The online survey, conducted by YouGov, combined standard survey questions as well as experiments¹ to gauge public opinion toward irregular migration and irregular migrants, to examine attitudes toward immigration, as well as and collect socio-demographic data.

The survey itself was developed collaboratively with the I-CLAIM consortium through workshops and consultations. It comprised 6 sections and 25 questions (see Table A.1 for a description of the questions included) that were tested and piloted before fieldwork. The final dataset also included demographic information from YouGov's panel of registered users (Abraham, 2025).

2.2. Target population, sample and fieldwork

The target population was the Dutch adult population (18+). Using “targeted quota sampling” from YouGov's panel, participants were selected to reflect the makeup of the Dutch population based on the following criteria: age; gender and education level; vote at the 2023 National Election; and region. YouGov provided sampling weights to ensure representativeness of the sample to the general population.

Fieldwork took place between 6th and 12th February 2025, yielding a sample of 1,052 respondents.

2.3. Data Analysis

The data was analysed using Stata, using the sampling weights. With regard to descriptive statistics of categorical variables, methods included percentage frequency distributions (using tabulations and cross-tabulations); chi-squared tests were used to check for a potential relationship between variables. None of the results presented are based on small cells (< 5). In terms of continuous variables, means and standard deviations were produced, using relevant methods (t-tests and ANOVA) to look at group differences. Survey experiments were analysed using Average Marginal Components Effects (AMCEs) (Hainmueller et al., 2014) to assess which attributes led to profile selection and Marginal Means (MMs) (Leeper et al., 2019) to look at group-based preferences. When relevant, missing information was excluded from the analyses, which led to variability in the sample size across analyses.

2.4. Survey respondents' main characteristics

Main characteristics of the Dutch survey respondents are covered here, and detailed results are in the appendix (Tables A.2-A.4). These characteristics allow us to draw a picture of the respondents and but also help us with identifying social groupings relevant for comparing knowledge and attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants. We first cover main respondent demographics (Table A.2).

In terms of the age, 34.6% of respondents were aged 18-39, 40.4% of respondents were in the middle age (40-64) category, and 25% over 65 years of age. The sample comprised 51 % female and 49% male

¹ Increasingly popular in migration studies (Sobolewska and Lessard-Phillips, 2024), survey experiments allow for a relatively unobtrusive measurement of public opinion on otherwise sensitive issues through the experimental manipulation of questions.

respondents. Among those who reported the information, 6% of respondents reported themselves as being a member of a minority ethnic group. The majority of respondents were either married or partnered (64.6%), and 36.6% lived in urban areas (the rest of respondents residing in suburban or rural areas). The geographical distribution of respondents was spread across the Netherlands, with more respondents residing in the West (47.5%) than in the rest of the country which is a representative distribution (21.3% in the South, 21.1% in the East and 10.1% in the North).

With regard to socio-demographic characteristics, Table A.3 shows that 26.8% of the Dutch respondents reported having low levels of education (up to lower secondary school), 38.4% having medium levels of education (upper and post-secondary but not tertiary), and 34.8% having high levels of education (tertiary level (universities and vocation schools (HBO))).

More than half of the sample were employed (56.5%) (either full-time or part-time), and 43.5% reported not being employed for various reasons (studies, retirement, child/family care, unemployment).

Among those providing a figure, 54.8% of the respondents were in a household with a low household income (less than 45.000 Euro per year), 35.3% with middle income (45.000-100.000 Euro per year) and 10% with a high income (more than 100.000 Euro per year).

Most respondents who reported voting in the 2023 election indicated having voted for the right wing populist Party for Freedom (PVV) (20%), followed by the GroenLinks/PvdA (13.4%), the Liberal Party (VVD) (13 %), and the New Social Contract (NSC) which is a Christian-democratic party founded in 2023 (11%). There were 14.9% of respondents who indicated they did not vote or preferred not to say.

In Table A.4, we outline respondents' experience with migration, which is topical given the focus of the survey. Analysis of these questions show that 4.7% of respondents indicated that they were born outside of the Netherlands, with 19.2% of respondents stating having some immigrant parentage (at least one parent born outside of the Netherlands). Furthermore, 12.5% of the sample indicated having lived abroad at some point and 47.2% indicated having friends who are immigrants.

Given the above-mentioned importance of social groups for the study of public perceptions, we will focus our analysis on difference across gender (male/female), age groups (18-39; 40-64; 65+), and political affiliation (PVV, GroenLinks/PvdA, VVD, NSC, Other parties, No vote) groupings.

2.4.1. *Views toward immigration*

Given the focus on irregular migration, we also give a brief overview of respondents' views toward immigrants and immigration in general. These views are particularly important given their potential links to migration-related attitudes and perceptions (Richards et al., 2025).

We were particularly interested in understanding how salient immigration was deemed a concern for the respondents themselves, as well as for their country of residence. In the survey, 46.7% of respondents designated immigration as an important issue for the Netherlands, and 31.6% as an important issue for themselves. These shares are relatively consistent with findings found elsewhere (Voogd et al. 2024, Ipsos I&O 2024).

Respondents were asked about their perceptions of the costs and benefits of migration in two areas, similar to those asked in the European Social Survey (Heath et al., 2016): (1) contribution of immigrants in terms of taxes and services (Figure 1) and (2) contribution of immigrants to the Netherlands' cultural life (Figure 2). Responses were recorded on a scale from 0 (more negative view) to 10 (more positive views), which were grouped into 3 categories: Negative (scores of 0-4); Neutral (score 5); and Positive (scores 6-10). Differences in views across key groupings (gender, age and political affiliation), were also examined.

Figure 1 shows that just over 40% of respondents had a negative view in terms of immigrants' contribution toward paying taxes and accessing services, implying that immigrants receive more than they contribute, whereas 45.6% of respondents indicated the opposite: that immigrants contribute more than they receive. Male respondents tended to hold a more positive view than female respondents, and views were broadly similar across age groups. Greatest variations were seen across political affiliation, with respondents aligned PVV having less positive views compared to others, and respondents aligned with GroenLinks-PvdA having more positive views.

Figure 1 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: immigrant take out/put in more (taxes and services). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=956.

Immigrants' contribution to the Netherlands' cultural life is explored in Figure 2. The figure shows that 34% of respondents expressed negative views toward immigrants' contribution to cultural life, and 50.1% expressed more positive views. Younger respondents expressed more positive views compared to middle-age respondents. The pattern across political affiliation is consistent with the previous figure, with PVV voters being more negative, and GroenLinks-PvdA voters being more positive in their view as to the contribution of immigrants to cultural life. NSC respondents also had a more negative view, especially compared with other voters.

Figure 2 Perceived costs and benefits of migration among I-CLAIM survey respondents: Cultural life undermined/enriched by immigrants. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=1,005.

3. Main Results

The details provided in this section above provide a clear overview of the survey respondents and their key characteristics and attitudes toward immigration and immigrants. This section, however, will focus on views toward *irregular* migration and *irregular* migrants, and providing answers to the following questions:

- 1) What does the public know about irregular migration and irregular migrants? [knowledge section]
- 2) What are public attitudes toward irregular migration and irregular migrants within the context of work? [attitudes section]

Each section will focus on addressing these questions through an exploration of relevant survey items, first for the whole sample, and then for each respondent grouping.

3.1. Knowledge of irregular migration and irregular migrants

This section looks at what respondents know about irregular migration and irregular migrants. We start by examining their awareness of irregular migration, its perceived scale, and how concerned they are about it, as well as situations that can lead to irregularity. We then shift to questions related to work, including the sectors where irregular migrants are thought to be employed and attitudes toward working irregular migrants.

3.1.1. *Scale and level of concern*

The scale of irregular migration in the Netherlands is relatively unknown. Recent estimates of irregular migrants in the Netherlands estimate their numbers as being between 23,000 and 58,000 people (van der Heijden et al. 2020), which represents between 1.4% and 3.6% of the foreign-born population (MIRREM, 2025). Being aware of this gap, we were interested in seeing how respondents would estimate the presence of irregular migrants as a share of all foreign-born individuals in the Netherlands. In Figure 3, we show how close respondents were to the estimates: either up to 10% above the estimated range (0%-14%); and '10% above the estimated range' (15% and over).

Just over 78% of Dutch respondents overestimated the share of irregular migrants by over 10%. There was a slight variation in the response patterns between male and female respondents (with female respondents overestimating the share of irregular migrants in the country more than male respondents), but not between age groups. Across political affiliation, PVV and non-voters had larger shares of overestimation of irregular migrants compared to GroenLinks-PvdA, and NSC voters, as well as non-voters.

Figure 3 Perception of the scale of irregular migration in the Netherlands against estimates. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=891.

The extent of irregular migration as a concern for respondents is explored in Figure 4. In the survey, respondents answered whether irregular migration was a concern for the Netherlands on a scale from 0 (not a concern) to 10 (a great concern). The proportion of Dutch respondents scoring over 5 on the question, is 69.3%. In terms of group differences, younger respondents did not see irregular migration as a concern as much as older groups. Respondents who voted centre or right-wing parties as well as non-voters indicated in larger shares that irregular migration was a concern for the Netherlands, this was especially the case for those who voted for the PVV compared to those who voted GroenLinks-PvdA, and for other parties.

Figure 4 Irregular Migration as concern for the Netherlands. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N=964 .

3.1.2. Becoming 'irregular': testing scenarios

Beyond gauging perceptions of the size of the irregular migrant population and its policy relevance, we also sought to understand what the public knows about the pathways into irregularity. To do so, we presented respondents with a range of scenarios that could, in principle, lead to irregular status, and examined how often they associated each scenario with becoming irregular.

The proposed scenarios were based on earlier research into the legal and policy frameworks that create irregularity (Hajer et al. 2024) and on political and media narratives surrounding irregularity in the Netherlands (Hajer 2024). This work highlights a mismatch between the process through which a migrant can become irregularised, what we refer to as the infrastructures of irregularity, and how this is portrayed in media and political narratives. The scenarios presented were: (1) someone with an expired student visa; (2) someone crossing a border without documentation; (3) someone waiting to hear back from their asylum claim; (4) someone born in the Netherlands to parents without legal residence; (5) someone hired through a recruitment company; (6) someone from the UK in-between contracts. Respondents were asked to state the likelihood of these scenarios occurring. Examining public perceptions of these scenarios is particularly relevant in light of I-CLAIM's work on narratives of irregularisation (Hajer 2024), which shows that, despite the many pathways into irregular status, political and media discourse overwhelmingly focuses on unauthorised border crossings and rejected asylum claims. These narratives not only narrow the

understanding of irregularity, as there are more ways of becoming irregular, but also tend to portray asylum seekers in a criminalising and negative manner.

Table 1 summarises how respondents evaluated the different scenarios and their links to irregularity. In each scenario, we report the share of respondents who considered it likely to result in irregular status (those selecting “most of the time” or “all of the time”), unlikely to do so (“never” or “sometimes”), and the share who indicated that they did not know whether the scenario could lead to irregularity.

Table 1 Scenarios of irregularity

		Likelihood of scenario leading to irregularity		Uncertainty regarding scenario (N=1,052)
		Never/ Sometimes	Most/all of the time	
Scenarios	Waiting to hear about their asylum claim (N=963)	15,9%	84,1%	8,2%
	Crossing a border without proper documentation (N=947)	36,8%	63,2%	9,3%
	Being hired through a recruitment company (N=888)	51,8%	48,2%	14,7%
	Being born in the Netherlands to parents who do not have legal residence status (N=917)	56,4%	43,6%	12,3%
	Having an expired student visa (N=793)	67,6%	32,4%	24,1%
	Being a worker from the UK in the EU (N=734)	75,2%	24,8%	28,8%

Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Across the scenarios, waiting for an asylum decision and crossing a border without documents were most frequently identified as leading to irregularity, mirroring patterns observed in media and political narratives. This stands out, given that asylum seekers who enter the Netherlands without authorization generally have a strong likelihood of obtaining the right to stay. In addition, the UN Refugee Convention explicitly states that irregular border entry should neither bar nor negatively influence the assessment of a claim for international protection.

If we look at the scenarios more closely, especially regarding group differences (Figures 5-8), we see some consensus as well as difference.

In terms of the most chosen scenario, waiting to hear about an asylum claim (Figure 5), we see that female respondents chose this scenario more often than male respondents. There were no clear differences in terms of political affiliation, despite GroenLinks-PvdA voters, with just over 88% of respondents saying this scenario leading to irregularity ‘most/all the time’, being among the most convinced that waiting for asylum decision may lead to irregularity.

Figure 5 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: waiting to hear about an asylum claim. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Turning to irregular border crossings (Figure 6), there is a distinction between male and female respondents, with female respondents choosing this scenario more often; and between middle-age and older respondents, the latter identifying this scenario as likely more often. In terms of political affiliations, fewer GroenLinks-PvdA voters saw this as a pathway to irregularity compared to other voters, with PVV voters having the highest share respondents seeing this as a pathway.

Figure 6 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: crossing a border without documentation. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Looking at the scenario of being the child of an irregular migrant (Figure 7), 43.6% of respondents identified this one as a likely pathway to irregularity, showing a difference across parties, with a higher share of PVV voters selecting this scenario as likely, especially compared to GroenLinks-PvdA and other voters. This is an interesting finding considering media attention over the past years for irregular migrant children, due to the *kinderpardon* (Hajer 2025). There were no large differences between the other groupings.

Figure 7 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: children born to parents without legal residence. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

Finally, with regard to the scenario of UK workers in the EU (Figure 8), similar shares of male and female respondents selected this scenario as likely. Younger respondents were more likely to select this scenario compared to middle-aged respondents. PVV voters were also more likely to choose this scenario, especially compared to GroenLinks-PvdA and NSC voters.

Figure 8 Evaluation of the scenarios leading to irregularity: EU workers in the UK. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

3.2. Irregular migrants and work: sectors & overall feelings

Given I-CLAIM’s focus on working conditions, we also explored respondents’ knowledge of irregular migration in the context of work and employment. They were asked to identify the main sectors of work where irregular migrants were believed to work and to share their feelings toward encountering irregular migrants in various settings.

Although 41.5% of respondents linked legal residence to work and employment, they still identified the main sectors where irregular migrants are thought to be employed (Table 2). For male irregular migrants, the most frequently mentioned sectors were agriculture, construction, transportation and cleaning. For female irregular migrants, the most mentioned sectors were cleaning, catering and hospitality, agriculture, and child and elderly care. These choices were generally consistent across all groups.

Table 2 Main sectors in which irregular migrants are deemed to work

	First	Second	Third	Fourth
Male	Agriculture	Construction/renovation	Transportation	Cleaning and other
Female	Cleaning and other	Catering and hospitality	Agriculture	Child/elderly care

Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025).

When given the opportunity to provide sectors themselves a free-text entries, a small number of respondents identified other sectors of relevance for the employment of irregular migrants in the Netherlands. These include the greenhouse horticulture sector, the meat industry, as well as sex work, especially for female irregular migrants.

Respondents were also asked their level of ease with having an irregular migrant engaged in work in their home, their workplace, and a shop, also known as social distance. They were asked to indicate how comfortable they would feel with having irregular migrants in these settings on a scale from 0 (would not mind at all) to 10 (would mind a great deal). The mean levels of answers provided is shown in Figure 9, providing a breakdown by main respondent grouping, with higher scores indicating that respondents would be more uncomfortable with having an irregular migrant in these settings.

The results from the figure show that, overall, respondents felt more social distance toward irregular migrants working in the same workplace. Social distance was higher in public or commercial encounters and lowest in private spaces such as the home and the workplace, and less social distance in a commercial setting. With regard to group differences, male respondents felt greater social distance than female respondents in all settings, and the youngest respondent group had lower levels of social distance than older groups. PVV and VVD voters had the highest mean level of social distance, with a slightly higher level of social distance for the home setting for PVV voters.

Figure 9 Social distance indicators. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). Baseline N= 926/917/961.

The focus on work sectors and feelings toward irregular migrants not only tells us a lot about public opinion regarding the matter, but also may help us make sense of overall attitudes toward irregular migrants within the context of work, which we explore in the next section.

3.3. Attitudes

We now we turn to more specific attitudes toward irregular migration in the context of work and employment, also considering how these intersect with race and gender. This focus is particularly relevant to I-CLAIM, where public perceptions and attitudes help shape narratives and contribute to the production of irregularity. In the survey, we explored these issues in several ways, including through survey experiments. As mentioned, experiments offer a relatively unobtrusive method for uncovering individual preferences on sensitive topics, such as irregular migration, while minimising bias.

In this section, we present findings from two experiments: one examining hiring preferences for irregular migrants and another assessing perceptions of irregular migrants' level of integration into Dutch society.

3.3.1. Hiring choice

The hiring choice experiment required respondents to choose between hypothetical applicants for a job caring for a relative. This scenario was selected because the care sector was frequently identified as a key area of work for irregular migrants. Each respondent was shown two pairs of applicants to hire, one male and one female, who shared certain characteristics but could not provide a residence permit for the Netherlands, indicating irregular status. Based on the information presented, respondents rated the likelihood of hiring

Figure 11 Results from hiring choice experiment. Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,052.

Figure 11 shows that, when hiring, respondents were less likely to choose to hire candidates from Morocco than from Brazil. This was consistent for both male and female applicants, with the male applicant from Morocco being even more less likely to be hired. Longer length of residence and recommendation from a friend were linked with likelihood of hiring. Applicants providing for their family based in the Netherlands were more likely to be chosen for hiring, compared to those who provided for a family in their country of origin. This was slightly stronger for female candidates.

Figures 12-14 show the overall popularity of specific attributes across different respondent groups using Marginal Means, which indicate how each individual attributes are favoured by types of respondent. Again, a marker to the right of the dotted line reflects a positive preference for a given attribute, while a marker to the left indicates a negative preference. Anything going across the dotted line is non-significant.

Figure 12 indicates that male and female respondents generally evaluate the attributes of domestic workers similarly when making (hypothetical) hiring decisions. There were, however, differences: male respondents were more positive toward Brazilian candidates compared to female respondents, while they viewed candidates from Morocco slightly more negatively. Female respondents, on the other hand, place greater (positive) importance on recommendation status compared to male respondents.

Figure 12 Attribute preference by gender of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,052.

Regarding respondents' age groups (Figure 13), most differences in the preferences can be observed at the country of the origin of applicants. Older respondent groups express much more negative preference for candidates from Morocco, as opposed to younger respondents for whom preference for Moroccan origin is not as negative. Middle-aged and older respondents shared preference for Brazilian and Filipino applicants, for younger respondents this was not significant.

Figure 13 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,052.

Finally, with regard to political affiliation (Figure 14), PVV and VVD voters expressed a stronger positive preference for the candidate from the Philippines. PVV, VVD and NSC voters expressed a negative preference for the Moroccan candidate. VVD and NSC voters expressed no strong preference for length of residence, whereas PVV and GroenLinks-PvdA voters did. All voters, with the exception of NSC voters, positively preferred the candidate that came recommended by a friend but negatively preferred candidates without a recommendation status. All voters positively favoured the candidates who have their family residing in the Netherlands, and negatively favoured those with family in the country of origin.

Figure 14 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, hiring choice experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1,052.

3.3.2. Perceptions of integration and settlement

Respondents' perceptions of the long-term settlement, or integration, of irregular migrants engaging in work was also explored within our experiments. This is particularly relevant because, while public discourse often focuses on newly arrived migrants, some irregular migrants have lived in the Netherlands for many years (and longer length of residence also seem to be positively evaluated as seen above). In addition, we considered perceptions of male irregular migrants, who are often portrayed most negatively in popular narratives.

As part of this, respondents were asked to assess the level of integration of two male irregular migrant profiles, one from Indonesia and one from Gambia, on a scale from 0 (not well-integrated at all) to 10 (very well-integrated). Each profile included a set of characteristics that were randomly varied to influence evaluations of integration (see Table A.6 for details). These characteristics included reason for migration, language fluency, religiosity, location of family and friends, and marital status. Figure 15 shows an example (translated into English) of what respondents saw.

Please read the profile provided and answer the question below it.

Lamin came to the Netherlands *from Gambia to get an education* but does not have legal residence. He is engaging in work and *does not speak* English fluently. *He regularly practices his religion*. His friends are mostly *the Netherlands*. *He is single*.

On a scale from 0 to 10, how well integrated, if at all, do you think *Lamin* is in UK's society?

0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
 Not well integrated at all Very well integrated
 Don't know

Figure 15 Experimental set up for perceptions of integration experiment (varying attributes in italics and blue for reference – see Table A.6 for details)

Results from this experiment are interpreted in the same manner as the previous one, with any markers to the left of the dotted line indicating a negative effect/preference, markers to the right indicating a positive effect/preference, and markers crossing the dotted line indicating a non-significant effect.

Figures 16 and 17 show the effect of specific attributes on the evaluation of integration, for both profiles (Figure 16) and by country of origin (Figure 17). The figures show that Dutch language fluency and the location of friends and family had a significant negative effect on evaluations of integration: profiles received a lower score if the person was not fluent in Dutch, compared to a profile indicating fluency, and if the person had friends and family in their country of origin compared to the Netherlands. Thus, aspects linked to Social integration as most relevant (Sobolewska, Galandini, and Lessard-Phillips, 2017). Moreover, the Indonesian profile received a slightly higher evaluation compared to the Gambian one.

Figure 16 Results from evaluation of integration experiment, all profiles (AMCEs). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=982.

Effects were relatively similar when looking at attributes for each origin separately (Figure 17), with slightly lower, but not different, effects for the Gambian profile, for some reasons for migration, language fluency, and location of friends and family.

Figure 17 Results from evaluation of integration experiment, by origin of profile (AMCEs). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=982.

Attribute preferences were also explored by respondent groups. In Figure 18, looking at differences between male and female respondents, we see few variations in preferences, aside from a slightly more positive preference for language fluency for male respondents, and a slightly more positive preference for the location of friends and family in the Netherlands for female respondents.

Figure 18 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=982.

In Figure 19, we see that the preferences for certain attributes were relatively similar across different age groups. Younger respondents showed a slight preference for country of origin (Gambia over Indonesia) compared with the two older groups who slightly preferred the Indonesian over the Gambian one (although not significantly different). They also showed a slightly more positive preference for the single profile. Overall, however, preferences were relatively consistent across all other attributes.

Figure 19 Attribute preference by age group of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means)
 Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=982.

Figure 20 shows differences across party affiliation. GroenLinks-PvdA voters expressed positive preferences for all of the attributes. VVD and NSC voters were also positive for most elements, and did not express negative preferences for any attributes, just less positive ones. PVV voters, who were not as positive in their preferences, held negative preference for lack of language fluency and location of friends and family. Language fluency was evaluated positively for integration. Between the voter groups the gaps between the various attributes are similar, yet the preferences are different. An exception here are NSC voters who favour language fluency and supporting a family in the Netherlands more positively than other party voters (gap is bigger).

Figure 20 Attribute preference by party affiliation of respondents, evaluation of integration experiment (Marginal Means). Source: I-CLAIM Survey (2025). N=1052.

4. Conclusion

This report presents findings from the I-CLAIM public perceptions survey on irregular migration, conducted in the Netherlands in February 2025 with a nationally representative sample of 1052 adults. The most outstanding results are:

All respondents significantly overestimated the number of irregular migrants within the Dutch foreign-born population.

While estimates suggest that irregular migrants account for between 1.4% and 3.6% of the total foreign born population, all respondents placed the figure significantly higher. The pattern of overestimation was particularly strong among older and right-leaning respondents.

Respondents strongly associated irregularity with unauthorised border crossings and pending asylum claims, reflecting dominant political and media narratives.

This finding is worrying because irregular border crossing should not preclude or negatively impact on the right to protection for asylum seekers. It was also found that children of undocumented migrants are widely perceived as invisible.

Respondents identified food delivery, construction, hospitality, cleaning, and care as the main sectors of irregular employment.

They added sex work in the open questions as a sector where it was expected to have many female irregular migrants working in the Netherlands.

Attitudes toward irregular migrants as workers were mixed.

In hiring experiments, respondents expressed pragmatic preferences: favouring candidates with longer Dutch residence, good recommendations, and family ties in the country, even if irregular. However, preferences were shaped by racialised hierarchies, with candidates from Morocco less favoured than those from Brazil.

These findings highlight the importance of addressing both misperceptions and the wider narrative environment that shapes public debates on irregularity.

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Appendices

Table A.1 Overview of the content of the I-CLAIM survey

Section	Description of question
A. Overall concerns	Top issues facing the country today
	Top issues facing you personally
B. Attitudes and experience toward immigration	Close friends as immigrants (split allocation)
	Whether immigrants take more in or out of society
	Whether cultural like undermined or enriched by immigrants
	Views on immigrants and work
C. Perception of irregular migration/migrants	Percentage of irregular migrants in country
	Whether irregular migration is a concern in country
	Work sector for female irregular migrants
	Work sector for male irregular migrants
	Scenarios of irregularity
D. Attitudes toward irregular migration and work/employment	List experiment on policy deservingness for female cleaner
	Conjoint experiment – <i>female care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Conjoint experiment – <i>male care workers</i>
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 1
	Likelihood of hiring applicant 2
	Choice of applicant
	Factorial experiment – <i>Evaluation of integration for male irregular migrant 1</i>
	Factorial experiment – <i>Evaluation of integration for male irregular migrant 2</i>
	Social distance indicator – <i>3 scenarios</i>
	E. Further demographics
Religiosity	
Member of ethnic minority group	
Has lived outside of country for over 1 year	

Table A.2: Main Demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Age (N=1,052)	Adult (18-39)	34.6%
	Middle Age (40-64)	40.4%
	Older adults (65+)	25.0%
Gender (N=1,052)	Male	49.0%
	Female	51.0%
Ethnic Minority (N=954)	No	94.0%
	Yes	6.0%
Marital Status (N=1,041)	Married, partnership, living as married, in a relationship	64.6%
	Divorced, widowed, separated	10.1%
	Single, other	25.3%
Location (N=1,052)	Urban	36.6%
	Suburban, rural	63.4%
Region (N=1,052)	North	10.1%
	East	21.1%
	West	47.5%
	South	21.3%

Table A.3: Socio-demographics

Characteristic	Categories	%
Education level (N=1,052)	Low	26.8%
	Medium	38.4%
	High	34.8%
Work status (N=1,052)	Working	56.5%
	Not working	43.5%
Household income (N=795)	Low	54.8%
	Medium	35.3%
	High	10.0%
Party voted for in 2021 (N=1,052)	PVV	20.0%
	GL-PvdA	13.4%
	VVD	13.0%
	NSC	11.0%
	D66	5.4%
	BBB	4.0%
	CDA	2.8%
	SP	2.6%
	Other	12.9%
DNV/DK	14.9%	

Table A.4: Respondents' Links to migration

Characteristic	Categories	%
Country of birth (N=1,039)	Outside of Germany	4.7%
	Germany	95.3%
Immigrant parentage (N=1,043)	None	80.8%
	One parent	5.9%
	Two parents	13.3%
Experience of migration (N=1,029)	No	87.5%
	Yes	12.5%
Has immigrant friends (N=1,030)	None	52.7%
	Yes, several	13.1%
	Yes, a few	34.1%

Table A.5 Attributes for hiring experiment randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN: FEMALE NAME/MALE NAME Two of three chosen for the female and male candidates.	Brazil: Fernanda/João Morocco : Khadija/Ahmed Philippines : Maria/Danilo
LENGTH OF RESIDENCE One of two.	under a year 5 years
RECOMMENDATION STATUS One of two.	<no recommendation> but comes recommended by a friend
LOCATION OF FAMILY One of two.	Country of origin Survey country

Table A.6 Attributes for integration experiments randomly selected for each profile.

COUNTRY OF ORIGIN/NAME One for each profile	Gambia :Lamin Indonesia : Bayu
REASON FOR MIGRATION One of four.	<no reason stated> to improve his living standards to get an education to seek protection
SURVEY COUNTRY LANGUAGE FLUENCY One of two.	speaks does not speak
RELIGIOSITY One of two.	He regularly practices his religion. <none stated>
LOCATION OF FRIENDS One of two.	From COUNTRY OF ORIGIN From SURVEY COUNTRY
FAMILY STATUS One of two.	He is single He has a family
LOCATION OF FAMILY If has family One of two.	In COUNTRY OF ORIGIN In SURVEY COUNTRY

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I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe